

DISTRIBUTION OF HEAT FLOW AND APPLICATION OF THE CONDENSATION EQUATION IN TURBINES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the condensation equation used to distribute heat flow in turbines is considered.

Comprehensive dynamic control equations for the T-60-112 turbine have been obtained. The methodology for their development is also applicable to other district heating (cogeneration) turbines.

If the following factors are neglected:

1. heat transfer along the tubes relative to the water, which is significant only in a small region near the water inlet to the heater;
2. the heat capacity of the tube metal and the condensate film on the tube surface (or these can be reduced to the heat capacity of the water),

then the following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \vartheta \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = \frac{T^H - T}{T_Z}, \quad (6)$$

Where T - water temperature in the pipe;

ϑ - speed ;

T^H - saturated steam temperature;

t - time;

T_Z the time constant of transverse heating, equal to the product of the heat capacity of water (per unit length of the tubes) and the thermal resistance to the transverse heat flow (over the same tube length)

$$T_Z = \frac{\rho c S l}{KF}$$

by applying the Laplace transformation ($t \rightarrow p$), we obtain an ordinary differential equation:

$$pT + \mathcal{G} \frac{dT}{dx} = \frac{T^H - T}{T_Z} \quad (2)$$

Solution of equation (2) under the boundary condition $T = T_0$, at $x = 0$:

$$T = \frac{T^H}{1 + T_Z p} + T_0 - \frac{T^H}{1 + T_Z p} e^{-\frac{1}{T_Z} + p \frac{x}{\mathcal{G}}} \quad (3)$$

We determine the heat flow by integrating over the entire length of the pipe:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= \frac{\rho c S}{T_Z} \int_0^\ell (T^H - T) dx = \frac{\rho c S}{T_Z} \int_0^\ell \left(\frac{T_Z p T^H}{1 + T_Z p} - T_0 + \frac{T^H}{1 + T_Z p} e^{-\frac{1}{T_Z} + p \frac{x}{\mathcal{G}}} \right) dx = \\ &= \rho c S \left[\frac{p T^H}{1 + T_Z p} \ell - T_0 \ell - \frac{T^H}{1 + T_Z p} \frac{\mathcal{G}}{1 + T_Z p} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{1}{T_Z} + p \frac{\ell}{\mathcal{G}}} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

The last exponential term can be neglected (due to the small value of underheating):

$$Q = \rho c S \frac{\ell p T^H - \mathcal{G} T_0 - \frac{T^H}{1 + T_Z p}}{1 + T_Z p}$$

Since the turbine operates without intermediate steam reheating, the steam in these extractions is always wet.

If it is approximately assumed to be saturated, and the heat flows into the steam and the casing are neglected, then by dividing the last expression by the constant average latent heat of vaporization for the steam flow rate, we obtain the desired condensation equation:

$$G^\circ \gamma = \frac{\rho c S \mathcal{G}}{r(1 + T p)} \left[\frac{\ell}{\mathcal{G}} p + \frac{1}{1 + T_Z p} \right] (T^H - T_0),$$

in which instead T^H you can enter a function π .

Method for calculating the parameters of the condensation equation. The values of the coefficients in the equations can be determined by calculation using the given formulas.

However, due to the complexity of heat transfer processes in the presence of a condensate layer on the tubes and possible fouling, it is preferable to rely on experimental data, which are commonly presented for heaters in the form of relative underheating characteristics:

$$\frac{\delta T}{\Delta T} = f(T_{cp}, W),$$

Where δT - underheating of water;

ΔT - heating water;

T_{cp} - average water temperature;

W - water consumption.

This characteristic is, of course, static. Therefore, we assume in (1) $p = 0$

$$Q = \rho c S (T^H - T_0) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}} \right)$$

Heat:

$$\Delta T = T - T_0 = \frac{Q}{\rho c S v} = (T^H - T_0) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z v}} \right),$$

underheating:

$$\delta T = T^H - T_0 - \Delta T = (T^H - T_0) e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}},$$

relative underheating:

$$\frac{\delta T}{\Delta T} = \frac{e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}}} = \frac{1}{e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}} - 1}$$

Where:

$$Z = e^{-\frac{\ell}{T_z \vartheta}} = 1 + \frac{1}{\frac{\delta T}{\Delta T}}$$

All the coefficients are then determined from the above formulas, in which the heat transfer coefficient is already expressed through the corresponding parameters.

The water chamber at the outlet represents a significant thermal capacity, whereas the volume of the inlet chamber in these heaters is relatively small.

If it is assumed that the water in the chamber, due to mixing and thermal conductivity, quickly becomes uniform in temperature, then:

$$\frac{d(\rho c V T)}{dt} = c \rho W (T' - T)$$

Where T' - incoming water temperature;

T - water temperature after mixing;

V - battery volume;

W - water consumption.

$$T_{ak} \frac{dT}{dt} + T = T', \quad \text{Where } T_{ak} = \frac{V}{W}$$

with volume $V = 4.4 \text{ m}^3$ and at an average value for the two main modes $W = 0.495 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{c}}$ we have:

$$T_{ak} = \frac{V}{W} = \frac{4.4}{0.495} = 8.9c$$

References:

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